

GLOBAL INTERNET TARMOG'IDAGI TAHDIDLARNING MAZMUN-MOHİYATI.

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Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrası o'qtuvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ma'naviy va axborot xurujlari kuchaygan davrda yashayapmiz. Bunday sharoitda tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishda huquq ta'limi ko'mak vazifasini bajaradi. Bunga ko'plab dalillarni keltirib o'tamiz.

Kalit so'z: internet, global, tahdid, xavf-xatar.

THE MEANING AND ESSENCE OF THREATS IN THE GLOBAL INTERNET NETWORK.

Abstract. We live in an era of increased spiritual and information attacks. In such conditions, Legal Education acts as a support in combating threats. Let's cite a lot of evidence for this.

Keyword: internet, global, threat, risk.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ УГРОЗ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ СЕТИ ИНТЕРНЕТ.

Аннотация. Мы живем в эпоху усиления моральных и информационных атак. В этих условиях юридическое образование выступает в качестве поддержки в борьбе с угрозами. Мы приводим множество доказательств этого.

Ключевое слово: интернет, глобальный, угроза, риск.

Bugungi kunda ma'rifiy adabiyotlarda "ma'naviy tahdidlar" tushunchasi keng ishlatib kelinmoqda. Avvalo bu tushunchaning mohiyatini anglab olish zarur. Ma'naviy tahdidlar - shaxs axloqiy ongida salbiy tushunchalar, tuyg'ular, xususiyatlar va sifatlarni hosil qiluvchi illatlar majmuidir. Chunki "tahdid" so'zi xavf-xatar, xuruj va buzish ma'nolarini anglatadi. Shu ma'noda ma'naviy tahdidlar shaxsni aqliy va axloqiy jihatdan buzishga qaratilgan maqsadli xurujlar hisoblanadi.

Hozirgi davrda jamiyat barqarorligini izdan chiqarishga qaratilgan tahdidlar va ularning oldini olish muammolarini tadqiq etish muhim nazariy va amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi. Zero, so'nggi yillarda global miqyos kasb etib jamiyatning barcha sohalarini qamrab olayotgan turli xavf-xatarlar vujudga keldi, ularning oldini olishning samarali yo'llarini aniqlash ustuvor vazifaga aylandi.

Jumladan, internetning ijtimoiy-falsafiy tahlili; zamonaviy jamiyatda internetdan foydalanish madaniyati va internetdagi taxdidlarning kirib kelishi, tuzilishi va ijtimoiy vazifalari talqini kabi yo'nalishlarda tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Rivojlangan davlatlardagi tadqiqot markazlari va institutlari tomonidan internetning rivojlanish bosqichlari, vaqtlar o'tishi bilan ijobiy tomonlaridan ko'ra salbiy jixatlarining ko'payishi va kelajak avlod tarbiyasiga jiddiy zarar yetkazish xolatlariga aloxida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Bunday tahdidlarni oldini olish maqsadida mamlakatimizda milliy madaniyat va ma'naviyatni yuksaltirish masalalariga a'loxida e'tibor berib kelinmoqda. Milliy qadriyatlarimizni tiklash, milliy san'at va ijod sohasida katta o'zgarishlar ro'y bermoqda. Bu ishlarni amalga oshirish yo'lida Respublika Ma'naviyat targ'ibot markazi hamda Milliy g'oya va mafkura ilmiy-amaliy markazi tashkil etildi. 2017 yilda mazkur tashkilotlar birlashtirilib, ular negizida Respublika

Ma'aviyat va ma'rifat markazi tashkil etildi. Bu ishlarning faolligini yangi bosqichga ko'tarish maqsadida O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha 2017-2021 yillarga mo'ljallangan harakatlar strategiyasining qabul qilinishi yurtimizda milliy madaniyat yuksaloyotgani hamda turli taxdidlarning oldini olish borasida keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilayotganidan dalolat beradi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2016 yil 14 sentabrdagi "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida"gi Qonuni, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 28 iyuldagi PQ – 3160-son "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish va soxani rivojlantirishni yangi bosqichga ko'tarish to'g'risida"gi va 2019 yil 3 maydagi PQ – 4307-son "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'rsida"gi qarorlari hamda mavzuga oid boshqa meyoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarda belgilangan vazifalarni amalga oshirishga mazkur dissertatsiya tadqiqoti muayyan darajada xizmat qiladi.

XXI asrga kelib turli oqimlar va kuchlar tomonidan inson ongi va qalbi uchun kurash yanada avj oldi.

Hozirgi tahlikali zamonda internet tarmog'i orqali tarqatilayotgan g'arazli ma'lumotlar, turli buzg'unchi g'oyalar, odob-axloqni yemiruvchi manfur illatlar har bir ongli kishini tashvishga solishi aniq.

Internet yordamida ishlar oson va tez bajariladi. Lekin keyingi paylarda internet bilan bog'liq buzg'unchiliklar, global tarmoqdan qabih maqsadda foydalanayotganlar ko'payib bormoqda. Oqibatda, zalolatga boshlovchi elektron nashrlar va videolavhalar keng yoyilmoqda. Asosiy muammo internetdan kim qanday maqsadda foydalanayotgan ko'payib bormoqda. Oqibatda, zalolatga boshlovchi elektron nashrlar keng yoyilmoqda.

Asosiy muammo internetdan kim qanday maqsadda foydalanishida. Xozir yosh bola xam kompyuterni bemalol ishlata oladi. Bir qarashda, buning yomon joyi yo'qday. Ammo haddan oshilsa, nazorat bo'shshsa, oqibati juda yomon bo'ladi.

Internetga kirayotgan yoshlar soni soat sayin ortmoqda. Bir muxim ma'lumot: "Bolalarni asraylik" (Save the Children) xalqaro tashkiloti AQShdagi 15-17 yashar o'smirlarning 85 foizi, Kanada yoshlarining 93 foizi internetdan muntazam foydalanishini e'lon qildi.

O'zbekistonda internetdan foydalanuvchilar soni 2008 yilda 2 million, 2014 yilda 10 million bo'lgan bo'lsa hozir 22.1 milliondan oshgani, ularning aksariyati yoshlar ekanini alohida qayd etish kerak.

Mamlakatimizning birinchi Prezidenti "Bugungi kunda noan'anaviy tahdidlar xalqaro mojarolarning qiyofasini butunlay o'zgartirmoqda va informatsion-psixologik xurujlar sezilarli xavf-xatar tug'dirmoqda. Ular armiyamizning negiziga putur yetkazish, avvalo, uning ma'naviy-axloqiy asoslariga ta'sir o'tkazishga urinish va shuningdek, zamonaviy internet texnologiyalardan foydalanish orqali bizning bunyodkorlik ruhidagi boy madaniyatimiz, ma'naviy qadriyat va an'analarimizga mutlaqo zid bo'lgan buzg'unchi g'oya va tushunchalarni yoshlarimizning ongu tafakkuriga singdirishga qaratilgani bilan ayniqsa xatarlidir" deb ta'kidlagan. Tahdidlar va ularga qarshi kurashish zarurati ekologik muammolardan ham dolzarbroq ahamiyatga ega bo'lib bormoqda.

Birinchi Prezidentimiz "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida ta'kidlanganidek, "...ma'naviyatga qarshi qaratilgan har qanday tahdid o'z-o'zidan mamlakat xavfsizligini, uning

milliy manfaatlarini, sogʻlom avlod kelajagini taʼminlash yoʻlidagi jiddiy xatarlardan biriga aylanishi va oxir oqibatda jamiyatni inqirozga olib kelishi mumkin” .

Biz gʻoyaviy, maʼnaviy va axborot xurujlari kuchaygan davrda yashayapmiz. Bunday sharoitda tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishda huquq taʼlimi koʻmak vazifasini bajaradi. Bunga koʻplab dalillarni keltirib oʻtamiz.

Birinchidan, hali voyaga yetmagan 2 yoshli bola issiq choynakda barmogʻini bexosdan bir marotaba kuydirib olsa, u choynakdan yiroq yuradi. Biroq, onasi sovutib bergan piyolaning suvini istagancha toʻkaveradi, piyolani sindirishga urinadi.

Bu qiyos bir qaraganda ilmiy qiyosga oʻxshamaydi. Ammo bildirmoqchi boʻlgan fikrimiz butunlay boshqa. Biz huquqqa hurmat tuygʻusi va mafkuraviy immunitetni eng avvalo oilada, mahallada, maktabgacha, umumiy oʻrta, oʻrta-maxsus va kasb-hunar taʼlimi muassasalarida shakllantirish orqali tahdidlarning har qanday turiga qarshi kurasha olamiz.

Ikkinchidan, yuqoridagi fikrning davomi sifatida taʼkidlash lozimki, tahdidlarga qarshi kurashishning huquqiy asoslari taʼlim muassasalaridagi darslik va oʻquv qoʻllanmalarida yetarlicha yoritilmayapti.

Uchinchidan, mavjud oʻquv adabiyotlarida mehnat qilish va oila qurish yoshi koʻrsatilgan. Yoshlarimiz bu toʻgʻrisida maʼlumot olishlari ijobiy holat. Biroq, taʼlim muassasasidagi oʻqishga taʼsir etadigan mehnat sharoitlarida ishlash mumkin emasligini ularga yetkazib berish pedagoglar oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan biridir. Oila kodeksiga koʻra, Oila qurishga yigitlarga 18 yoshdan, qizlarga esa 17 yoshdan yoʻl qoʻyilar edi. Emanspatsiya holatiga koʻra bu raqamlar yana bir yilga qisqarishi mumkin edit. Ushbu yoshda voyaga yetmaganlarning taʼlim muassasasida tahsil olayotganligiga ham eʼtiborimizni qaratishimiz lozim. Bu holat yigit va qizlarimizning taʼlim muassasasidagi faoliyatiga salbiy taʼsirini oʻtkazar edi. Qonunchilikdagi oʻzgarishlarga muvofiq nikoh yoshining tenglashtirilishi bu muammoning yechimi boʻldi.

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